

Understanding the Skills and Pathways Behind Research Software Training

ISC 2023 - BoF Session

Some questions about training...

- All responses are anonymous
- Responses will be shared on screen
- Helps us to understand the BoF audience
- Your chance to provide your views/perspectives

How would you define your role(s) in the context of training (select all that apply)

How easy do you feel it is to find/access research software training material within your organisation?

How easy do you feel it is to find/access research software training material online?

How easy do you feel it is to combine training materials that you're aware of into a coherent pathway?

What do you feel are the most frequently overlooked research software skills?

59 Answers

Mentimeter

Writing documentation

Communication

CI/CD

debugging

Testing software

Project managing

Low level programming
Presentation skills

Submit scripts, data management

Documentation

What do you feel are the most frequently overlooked research software skills?

59 Answers

Mentimeter

Basic terminal usage

Documentation writing

Building software, debugging builds

Profiling

Licences and documentation

Negotiation skills with researchers

Understanding hardware architecture

Advanced version control

Critical thinking

What do you feel are the most frequently overlooked research software skills?

59 Answers

Mentimeter

Independence

Communication

Industry awareness

Reproducibility

Software design

Documentation

Managing big collaborations

Project Planning

How to organise different projects/workload planning

What do you feel are the most frequently overlooked research software skills?

59 Answers

Mentimeter

Performance engineering

engineering as opposed to just coding

Usage of PGO, LTO, CI, sanitizers, ...

Non-technical and engineering-adjacent skills, such as project management, feature builds, GitOps/FinOps

Adherence to best practices, documentation and reusability

Getting insight from other areas of research

Software Engineering

Evaluating of scalability and efficiency

Communication
Open minded
Endurance

What do you feel are the most frequently overlooked research software skills?

59 Answers

Mentimeter

Reproducibility

debugging parallel code

System Design

Optimising CPU usage/ efficiency

Computational resource estimation

Finding existing code to integrate ndy extend

Presentation skills

unit testing

Plugging in multiple softwares together to make project more robust

What do you feel are the most frequently overlooked research software skills?

59 Answers

Mentimeter

Packaging

Performance optimisation

Bake it into induction

Promote training broadly

Well organized pages through a provider like atlassian

Interaction with AI assistant

Encourage use of time/effort devoted to training itself

Dissemination in cooperation with educational institutions

Lower prices for training books

What do you feel are the most frequently overlooked research software skills?

59 Answers

Widely shared introductory blog posts etc. with a set of recommended topics

Openness to basic questions

Encourage users (not just developers) to post their scripts/ code online as part of documentation

Scheduler training especially less used

Version conflict

How do you think training material (especially for overlooked skills) can be made easier to discover?

40 Answers

Mentimeter

Mentoring

Well known central platform/repository

Guest lectures

Curated repositories?

Building and fostering relationships to raise awareness

Single European Training Portal

Too many different outlets. Consolidate and have a single wiki / Outlet

Open door days

Coherent tagging

How do you think training material (especially for overlooked skills) can be made easier to discover?

40 Answers

Mentimeter

Creating incentives for improving skill sets

Centralised sites with lists/links to resources

Unified improved search scientific search engine

Tagged lists

Curating content, maybe into "courses"

an online graph-based database

Most people dont know which skills are important - they dont know what to look for

One European-wide central place

A hub for RSE training material (eg. Europe-wide)

How do you think training material (especially for overlooked skills) can be made easier to discover?

40 Answers

Mentimeter

Trusted central locations with overview articles and pointers to deeper dives

Centralised list with up to date links to different sources

Collaborations with like-minded orgs to share info

listed on internal documentation

Consistent terminology

Partnerships with research and academic organizations, many of whom have informal internal training offerings, which don't necessarily evolve or scale well over time

Links between training providers

Seminar (series)

Promote training broadly

How do you think training material (especially for overlooked skills) can be made easier to discover?

40 Answers

Mentimeter

Dissemination in cooperation with educational institutions

Industry (vendor) collaborations (KTP)

User forums

One main online source to find good sources on various topics

Encourage use of time/effort to devote on training

Interactive AI assistant

Use modern social media for advertising

Encourage users (not just developers) not post their code online in the documentation

User groups

How do you think training material (especially for overlooked skills) can be made easier to discover?

40 Answers

Mentimeter

integration with postgraduate coursework

Passing experience on: on / Off boarding

Conflicts with deadlines

Finding the best keywords terminology for an unfamiliar topic

What challenges have you faced in accessing relevant training content?

38 Answers

Mentimeter

Out of date

Lack of time

Paywall

Paywalled

Too many slack workspaces

Finding materials with non-trivial code examples

Training content is too verbose

Getting the right contents and the level of detail

Inappropriate format for self learning, e.g. slides

What challenges have you faced in accessing relevant training content?

38 Answers

Mentimeter

Not general enough or out of date info

Reproducibility

Formats that I don't personally like - e.g. video when I want text.

Too many different portals

too many internal rules that make it difficult to follow external training materials

There are too many different sources and very little help in judging which are good ones

Paywalls

Find hardware to run materials o

Prices for external training material (books, published guides)

What challenges have you faced in accessing relevant training content?

38 Answers

Mentimeter

Access to hardware

Different time scopes of training materials

Assess quality of the material beforehand

The answer wasn't on StackOverflow :
(

outdated examples

Material is generally very basic, corner cases are missing

Documentation is not open, or not existent

Validated content

Not available freely

What challenges have you faced in accessing relevant training content?

38 Answers

Mentimeter

Conflicts with project deadlines

Good material is often not fully online, requires advance sign up notice

Site specific configurations not translating to your site

Time needed to figure out the scope of the accessible content

Too basic to apply to more complex topics

Long-term access to training platforms

Quality and Relevance

Different versions don't link or are not compatible

All start with the basics

What challenges have you faced in accessing relevant training content?

generalising to other environments

differences in module
setup/environment between SC
centers

38 Answers

Mentimeter

What challenges have you faced in linking training content from different sources?

31 Answers

Mentimeter

Licensing

link rot - pages disappearing

Broken links

I'm unsure about licences

Detail doesn't match local systems/applications

Most training events don't have public training material

Not consistent notation

Overlap of material

Incompatible or different packages

What challenges have you faced in linking training content from different sources?

31 Answers

Verifying information with experience and professional opinion

Competing standards (programming languages, APIs, research practices)

Terminology and nomenclature used

badly structured documentation pages

A lot of legacy material to dig through

Varying versions of software

It is difficult to connect different topics together without a path to follow

All start with the same basics

Different pathways of teaching

What challenges have you faced in linking training content from different sources?

31 Answers

Mentimeter

Different versioning can't link or are not compatible

Knowledge gap between basic and advanced

Materials being too specific to a single problem/system/domain

Reconciling enterprise software practice with research needs/resources

Joining Presence vs offline vs online Material

Lack of detail when following community examples - very specific for one use case but not generalisable

Differences in modules/environment between SC centres.

Overhead in making good training material is not recognized

Open stack

What challenges have you faced in linking training content from different sources?

31 Answers

Mentimeter

How to pass experience asking in a good fashion

MPI

Quantum

Machine learning

What skill(s) in the research software / HPC space do you want to learn next?

35 Answers

Mentimeter

DevOps

Licenses

HPC Profiling skills

Rust

linking libraries correctly

Julia

Container

AI/ML, using GPUs properly

Julia

What skill(s) in the research software / HPC space do you want to learn next?

35 Answers

Mentimeter

Best practices for portable GPU software development

HPC & Quantum

Parallel Programming

Using AI to develop code efficiently

GPU programming

Profiling and resource usage optimization

HPC-QC Integration and Heterogeneous systems

C++ executors

Workflow orchestration

What skill(s) in the research software / HPC space do you want to learn next?

35 Answers

Mentimeter

Run stable diffusion locally

Developing applications for multi node

SYCL

Coding practices

Hardware software codesign

How to leverage specialized hardware, dpu IPU

Debugging on clusters.

Rust/Go

Quantum algorithms

What skill(s) in the research software / HPC space do you want to learn next?

35 Answers

Mentimeter

Compiler development

Working with containerised workflows

Nim

Vendor-independent GPU programming

MPI

Self-hosting/training LLMs

Spack

Machine learning

Thanks for participating

We hope you enjoyed this interactive part of the session.